

MAELSTROM

MArInE Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management

D2.6

Guidelines on how to consider ML pollution and remediation in marine spatial planning

31/12/2023

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Executive Summary

The MAELSTROM project aims to test and evaluate innovative technologies for the removal of marine litter in different coastal environments, also assessing their impact on the ecosystems in chosen demo sites and evaluating the economic and societal benefits of the MAELSTROM solutions within local economies. Treatments of the plastic litter for their recovery within a circular economy concept are also foreseen. The purpose of this deliverable is to provide an overview on marine litter (ML) management relevant concepts for marine and coastal planners, managers and decision makers. The concepts of ML sources and impacts are illustrated, together with key elements regarding ML management, from pollution prevention, monitoring and remediation. An overview is provided on if and how ML topic is considered in the plans developed by European countries under the Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) Directive (overview based on some example countries only). MSP plans, even if they do not address ML directly, recognize it as a critical anthropogenic pressure and maritime activities (fisheries, shipping, etc) as important sources of ML too. Some MSP plans address specifically the need to contribute to ML pollution prevention by including objectives and measures targeting maritime sectors and activities. A growing need for integration between MSFD and MSPD can be recognized, as well as a stronger linkage between WFD and MSFD too, with particular regard to the topic of ML pollution. Suggestions are provided to marine planners and practitioners for possible actions from their side (across the entire planning process) to contribute to strengthen these interlinkages and help tackle marine litter pollution.

Key recommendations include analysing existing conditions by incorporating ML data from sources like the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) monitoring, engaging in dialogue with relevant institutions and stakeholders, and capitalising on studies addressing ML spatial distribution. Emphasis should be focused on understanding the role of maritime and coastal activities as ML sources, identifying high-impact areas, and including ML pollution in land-sea-interaction analysis under MSP. These measures collectively enhance the integration of ML pollution concerns into comprehensive marine management strategies. The planned development should encompass the identification of objectives and a combination of spatial and non-spatial measures, with a specific focus on preventing ML pollution from maritime sectors. Synergies with ML pollution measures outlined in the Program of Measures (PoM) under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) should be enhanced. In

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the presence of knowledge gaps, enhanced efforts should be proactively included in plans, like provisions for monitoring and studies addressing ML pollution sources and impacts associated with maritime activities. This would ensure a robust and well-informed approach to addressing ML pollution in the maritime domain.

Multiple sectoral stakeholder engagement is crucial in supporting all MSP stages, contributing to understanding the economic impacts of ML pollution on maritime sectors. These initiatives also include coordinating with mainland actors to address ML sources, promoting sector participation in citizen science, and encouraging educational initiatives. The dialogue shall also emphasise ML prevention options and prioritise remediation of ML hotspots impacting maritime activities. This comprehensive approach is critical to ensure informed decision-making across all MSP stages.

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
ALDFG	Abandoned, lost or otherwise discarded fishing gear
APA	Agência Portuguesa do Ambiente
APEC	Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation
CMVC	Câmara Municipal Vila do Conde
COVID	Coronavirus disease
D10	Descriptor 10
D10C1	Descriptor 10 – Criteria 1
D10C2	Descriptor 10 – Criteria 2
D10C3	Descriptor 10 – Criteria 3
D10C4	Descriptor 10 – Criteria 4
DC	Coastal defence
DFG	Derelict fishing gear
DGP	Provincial Council Resolution
DGPM	Directorate General for Sea Policy
DGR	Regional Council Resolution
DGRM	General-Directorate for Natural Resources, Security and Maritime Services
DRAAC	Regional Directorate for the Environment and Climate Change
DRAM	Regional Directorate for Marine Affairs
EC	European Commission
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zone
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EPR	Extended Producers Responsibility
EU	European Union
GES	Good Environmental Status
GT	Gross tonnage
ICNF	Institute for Conservation of Nature and Forestry
IMC	Ionian-Central Mediterranean
INE	National Statistics Institute
IPMA	Portuguese Institute of Sea and Atmosphere
IPPC	Integrated Pollution Prevention and Control
IT	Italy/Italian
JRC	Joint Research Centre
LR	Regional law

Acronym	Meaning
LSI	Land-sea interaction
MARPOL	International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships
MIS	Measure
ML	Marine litter
MM	Minister of Maritime Affairs
MO	Western Mediterranean
MPA	Marine Protected Area
MS	Member State
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
MSP	Maritime Spatial Planning
MSPD	Maritime Spatial Planning Directive
N2K	Natura 2000
NAZ	National
NGO	Non-governmental organization
NM	Nautical mile
NMPF	National Marine Planning Framework
NW	North-west
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OMPP	Overarching Marine Planning Policies
OS/OSP	Specific objective
OSPAR	OSPAR Commission (originally, Oslo and Paris Conventions)
OTB	Bottom otter trawl
PBDE	Polybrominated diphenyl ethers
PCB	Polychlorinated biphenyl
PSOEM	Maritime Space Planning Situation Plan
PT	Portugal
RNAP	National Network of Protected Areas
SCI	Site of Community
SDG14	Sustainable Development Goal 14
SEA	Strategic Environmental Assessment
SLR	Sea level rise
SMPP	Sectoral Marine Planning Policies
SRAAC	Secretariat for Environment, Natural Resources and Climate Change
SRD	Sewage Related Debris
SRMCT	Regional Secretariat of the Sea, Science and Technology

Acronym	Meaning
SS	Sustainable Development
SUP	Single-Use Plastics
TBB	Bottom beam trawl
TM	Maritime transport
UN	United Nations
UNEP	United Nations Environment Program
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
WFD	Water Framework Directive
ZEC	Special Area of Conservation

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1 Introduction to the MAELSTROM project

MAELSTROM is a project funded under the Topic CE-FNR-09-2020 Pilot action for the removal of marine plastics and litter. MAELSTROM strives to provide answers and diversified solutions to the complex question of the removal and sustainable treatment of marine litter (ML) legacy. MAELSTROM contemplates the integration of complementary technologies for marine litter removal in different European coastal ecosystems, compounded with a full-fledged circular economy and societal-oriented solutions. In particular, the project (i) sets out a reliable multidisciplinary and scientifically sound approach for the assessment of marine debris distribution and impact on marine life in highly valuable ecosystems and protected areas; (ii) designs and manufactures scalable, replicable and automated technologies, co-powered with renewable energy and second generation fuel, to identify, remove and sort ML; (iii) evaluates over time the performance of ML removal devices along with their impact on local ecosystems; (iv) integrates different technologies to track, sort and recycle all types of collected ML into valuable raw materials for future marketisation; (v) assesses the economic and societal impact of the MAELSTROM solutions providing also a comprehensive life-cycle assessment of the technologies and products; (vi) enhances social awareness about the ML issue and engages citizens and stakeholders in MAELSTROM activities; (vii) interplays with similar projects to maximise innovation uptake for ML removal within and outside the EU.

2 MAELSTROM Consortium

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3 Policy context for marine and coastal planning

The Directive 2014/89/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing a framework for maritime spatial planning (the Maritime Spatial Planning Directive - MSPD) defines maritime spatial planning (MSP) as a process by which the relevant Member State (MS) authorities analyse and organise human activities in marine areas to achieve ecological and socio-economic objectives. This Directive identifies minimum requirements for the establishment of maritime spatial plans, including considerations regarding land-sea interactions, the ecosystem-based approach, coherence between MSP and other processes such as integrated coastal management, the involvement of stakeholders, the consideration of the best available data, and transboundary cooperation between Member States, and with third countries.

The main objective of MSP (par. 19) is to promote sustainable development and to identify the utilisation of maritime space for different sea applications as well as to manage spatial uses and conflicts in marine areas. Notwithstanding this, MSPD recognizes (par. 13) that marine waters, ecosystems and marine resources are subject to significant pressures due to multiple human activities, as well as climate change effects, natural hazards and shoreline dynamics. The Directive indicates (par. 13) that due regard should be given to such pressures in the establishment of maritime spatial plans. In fact, healthy marine ecosystems and their multiple services, if integrated into planning decisions, can deliver substantial benefits in terms of food production, recreation and tourism, climate change mitigation and adaptation, shoreline dynamics control and disaster prevention, the so-called ecosystem services. The scope of MSP covers the marine space under the MS jurisdiction (until the limits of the exclusive economic zone (EEZ) or the continental shelf).

Both MSPD and the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) are part of the EU's overarching *Integrated Maritime Policy* (IMP). Thus, links between the two Directives are multiple: application of an ecosystem-based approach, achievement and maintenance of Good Environmental Status (GES), sustainable exploitation of natural resources and sustainable development of maritime activities in general. MSP is recognized as a key tool to achieve the MSFD's GES objectives for EU waters and to help in the preservation of biodiversity (European Commission, 2022). To support MS in this process, the EU Commission issued guidelines for implementing an ecosystem-based approach in MSP (European Commission et al., 2021), which provide many

elements regarding the integration of MSFD objectives in MSP. The implementation of the MSPD targets foresees the sustainable development of maritime sectors in accordance with the achievement of the GES. Integrating all the blue economy sectors and activities, the MSP process should be able to regulate maritime activities, resolve or mitigate sea-use conflicts, and promote the implementation of management measures that reinforce the achievement of GES, with the support of an ecosystem-based approach.

Paramana et al. (2023), performed a study on which the MSFD and the MSPD were compared and their interlinkages analysed. They concluded that streamlining the MSFD with the MSPD is crucial to ensure that the introduction or expansion of human activities in the marine environment are sustainable. The authors noticed that the two directives can be optimally implemented only when integrated, while their synergy and coherence can better ensure the achievement of the European IMP objectives.

Most of the activities that take place in the marine environment also have an onshore component or impact. An alignment between the maritime and the terrestrial spatial planning is therefore important and should be achieved through consistency of policies, plans and management. In this regard, the MSPD indicates land-sea interaction (LSI) as one of the minimum requirements for MSP plans. The appropriate planning and management of LSI is also highly related to the economic benefits of MSP and the importance of given maritime uses covered by the MSP for the economic development of the region in question. Integration of terrestrial and marine planning through LSI analysis has been the object of several studies suggesting methodological approaches and providing examples of application (e.g. Smith et al., 2011; Kidd et al., 2019; 2020; Asprogerakas et al., 2020; Morf et al, 2022; Bocci et al., 2024).

The importance of considering land and sea connection is of particular relevance when considering pollution issues since land-based activities are the most important sources for all kinds of marine pollution, including litter.

As far as MSFD is concerned, ML which is defined as *“any solid material that is man-made and enters the marine environment directly or indirectly, intentionally or unintentionally”* is considered through Descriptor 10: Properties and quantities of marine litter do not cause harm to the coastal and marine environment, which is addressed through four criteria¹. From a pollution prevention perspective, the most

¹ Criteria are as follows:

recent and relevant policy is the Zero pollution vision of the European Union for 2050, which targets the reduction of air, water and soil pollution to levels no longer considered harmful to human health and natural ecosystems (One Health concept), and allows creating a toxic-free environment. The Zero pollution action plan has set two targets for 2030 related to plastic pollution: (a) reducing by, at least, 50 % plastic litter at sea and (b) reducing by, at least, 30 % microplastics released into the environment. This Action plan constitutes one of the pillars of the European Green Deal.

In such a context, the Water Framework Directive (WFD) represents a third fundamental pillar in achieving integrated planning and management. Soininen & Platjouw (2018) highlighted how WFD, MSFD and MSPD all seek the ecosystem approach to aquatic governance with complementary viewpoints. The authors noted that the WFD and the MSFD prioritise ecological goals within that ecosystem approach, while the MSPD seeks to reconcile the ecosystem approach with the sustainable blue economy.

Within this policy context, it seems fundamental to improve the interconnections between those policies that are extremely relevant for the management of the marine and coastal environments.

The scope of this deliverable is to provide marine planners and managers with a synthetic view of the ML problem and illustrate the opportunities, for the sectors that they deal with, to contribute to solve ML related issues.

D10C1 – Primary: The composition, amount and spatial distribution of litter on the coastline, in the surface layer of the water column, and on the seabed, are at levels that do not cause harm to the coastal and marine environment. MS shall establish threshold values for these levels through cooperation at Union level, considering regional or sub regional specificities

D10C2 – Primary: The composition, amount and spatial distribution of micro-litter on the coastline, in the surface layer of the water column, and in seabed sediment, are at levels that do not cause harm to the coastal and marine environment MS shall establish threshold values for these levels through cooperation at Union level, considering regional or subregional specificities.

D10C3 – Secondary: The amount of litter and micro-litter ingested by marine animals is at a level that does not adversely affect the health of the species concerned. MS shall establish threshold values for these levels through regional or sub regional cooperation.

D10C4 – Secondary: The number of individuals of each species which are adversely affected due to litter, such as by entanglement, other types of injury or mortality, or health effects. MS shall establish threshold values for the adverse effects of litter, through regional or sub regional cooperation.

4 State of play: consideration of marine litter issues in marine planning

This chapter describes how the ML issue is considered in marine plans of some European (EU) MS). A focus is provided on the countries directly involved in the MAELSTROM project: Italy and Portugal. Some complementary elements are also included for other EU MS. This information was added based on a survey undertaken by consulting with MSP experts across the EU, with the support of a questionnaire (see Annex 1). The purpose of this chapter is to supply examples on whether and how this topic is addressed by the plans in place, in order to identify gaps and opportunities for reinforcement of provisions aiming at ML pollution reduction with the next round of MSP plans.

4.1 Marine litter in the Italian Maritime Spatial Plans

The present review is based on the drafts of the Italian MSP plans². Italy has developed three drafts of its MSP plans (hereafter referred to as the plans), made available for public consultation on 15th September 2022. The three plans refer to the following maritime areas of the Mediterranean Sea: the “Tyrrhenian - Western Mediterranean”, the “Ionian - Central Mediterranean” and the “Adriatic”. The plans apply to the territorial waters up to 12 NM (nautical miles), the continental shelf and the ecological protection zone of the North-Western Mediterranean, the Ligurian Sea and the Tyrrhenian Sea. The consultation process was closed in December 2022. On the 7th of November 2023, the Ministry of Environment and Ecological Transition published the Decrees concluding the SEA process of the three plans, including a series of observations and recommendations to be included in the plans that are now under revision.

In the policy overview presented in the plans the strategy towards zero pollution (COM(2021) 400 final) is not directly addressed but pollution prevention is targeted under other strategies and plans (e.g. River Basin Management Plans under the WFD and the MSFD) to which the MSP plans refer to.

The plans’ **vision** includes a mention to the fight against marine pollution to be undertaken with the contribution from all maritime sectors - transport, offshore

² Available at <https://www.sid.mit.gov.it/login>

activities, fisheries, aquaculture and tourism in particular – which are directly involved in the reduction of polluting emissions into the air and water, and in the dispersal of waste at sea and the introduction of alien species. Moreover, the recovery of waste at sea and related recycling activities is mentioned as one of the perspectives for blue economy development. More specifically, waste dispersion prevention is targeted in relation to maritime traffic developments: in the perspective of further growth of this sector, the plans aim to support the strengthening of measures to reduce the environmental impacts, including water and air pollution, emission of climate-altering substances, dispersion of waste, underwater noise emission, and introduction of alien species, in line with the measures provided under the MARPOL Convention (International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships).

ML pollution prevention is targeted by some of the strategic objectives of the plans (objectives defined at a national level and valid for the entire plan domain):

- OS_SS|02 – Contributing to the National Strategy for Sustainable Development: The actions of the Plan contribute to the achievement of SDG14 (Life under water) by strengthening all marine pollution prevention measures (air, water, waste, introduction of invasive alien species);

OS_SS|04 – Fully seize the economic and environmental sustainability opportunities that derive from the circular economy: The plans promote the opportunities offered by the circular economy approach to marine and maritime activities, encouraging, among other things, initiatives that aim at the prevention, recovery and recycling of ML;

OS_TM|02 – Promoting the use of alternative fuels, reducing discharges into the sea, improving port facilities for the collection of waste and cargo residues and/or encouraging the use of such facilities, improving the management of dredged sediments: The plans, in line with Directive 2000/59/EC, support the general objective of reducing discharges into the sea of waste produced by ships and cargo residues, in particular illicit discharges, by improving the availability and use of port reception facilities for the waste and residues and thus strengthening the protection of the marine environment.

In addition to the strategic objectives valid at national level, the plans identify specific objectives for the sub-areas by the coastal regions involved in the planning process.

Sub-areas are marine areas in territorial waters, extending in front of each coastal region. Several specific objectives target ML pollution prevention.

For example, for the Gulf of Taranto, Calabria, Basilicata and Apulia region, the following specific objectives have been identified:

(IMC/4)OSP_N|04 – Promote management actions for waste found at sea and on beaches (better waste management, reduction of packaging waste, increase in recycling rates, improvement of wastewater treatment, promotion of recovery activities for waste already dispersed);

(IMC/4)OSP_P|03 – Promote the reduction of the use of plastic materials in the fishing and aquaculture sectors, strengthen interventions aimed at promoting the recycling of waste products and the correct disposal of waste deriving from fishing and aquaculture activities.

Sardinia region has identified the following specific objective:

(MO/7)OSP_N|04 – Promote the circular economy linked to waste from the sea and that produced in ports.

Liguria region has identified the following specific objective:

(MO/1)OSP_DC|07 – Promote management actions for waste found in the sea and on beaches.

Campania region has identified the following specific objective:

(MO/4)OSP_T|02 – Promote and encourage redevelopment of seaside tourism in terms of energy and water efficiency and waste reduction, and establish the criteria for the use of state-owned areas for tourist and recreational purposes.

And finally, Apulia region has identified the following specific objective:

(A/6)OSP_N|05 – Promote waste management actions found at sea and on beaches, through policies to combat "Marine Litter", which include better waste management, the reduction of packaging waste, the increase in recycling rates (plastic in particular), the improvement of wastewater treatment, and the promotion of recovery activities for already dispersed waste.

The plans also include a list of measures at national level, valid for the entire domain of the maritime plans, identifying actions to meet the strategic objective. Some of these measures are related to ML, such for example:

NAZ_MIS|44 – Produce a study aimed at identifying the areas of greatest concentration ("hot spot" areas) of the pressures generated in the marine environment by maritime traffic: atmospheric emissions, water pollution, waste dispersion, underwater noise emissions, and collisions with marine megafauna.

NAZ_MIS|48 – Actively contribute to harmonisation initiatives on a European and Mediterranean scale of the methods of solid waste collection on ships and their disposal in ports, in order to optimise procedures (from the planning phase to the awarding phase of services), maximise the recyclable fractions, and contribute to the development of circular economy supply chains. Particular attention must be paid to plastic waste, to activities to combat the abandonment of this waste in the sea and on beaches, to the related collection and recovery activities and to environmental education and information activities.

At the regional level (sub-areas) some regions have identified specific measures to be applied to their sea area of competence. Friuli-Venezia Giulia region has provided a lot of emphasis on ML in the part of the plan of its direct competence. The region has identified the following measures:

(A/1)_MIS|3 – Development of circular economy strategies aimed at promoting the reduction, recycling and reuse of waste from maritime activities including: creation of port and coastal waste collection facilities suitable to meet the needs of ships that regularly use the port combined with options such as deposit-refund systems, extended producer responsibility schemes and recycling targets;

(A/1)_MIS|4 – Support for the prevention and reduction of the impact of plastic at sea: uptake of innovative solutions to prevent and minimise marine plastics and microplastics, replacement of alternative materials to plastics in the equipment of fishing vessels and in aquaculture, use of products with a circular design that promotes durability and repairability, reducing waste and side effects such as the accidental capture of fish, and solutions for monitoring and recovering the accidental loss of containers from ships and fishing equipment;

(A/1)_MIS|7 – Support for activities aimed at recovering waste intercepted during fishing activities, cleaning of seabed and beaches (for example, aMare Friuli-Venezia

Giulia region project, referred to in art. 5 of LR 26/2020, or support for similar initiatives).

Sardinia region has also identified a measure dealing with ML:

(MO/7)_MIS|31 – Carry out, in line with the provisions of the National Strategy for the circular economy, an action of collection and dissemination of best practices in the field of circular economy connected to waste coming from the sea and that produced in ports.

In conclusion, if marine pollution prevention, reduction and remediation are at the boundaries of the scope of MSP, being more directly targeted by MSFD and WFD, the Italian draft plans offer several entry points to the management of these important environmental issues and pave the way for implementation actions where the economic sectors can have an active role.

4.2 Marine litter in the Portuguese Maritime Spatial Plan

The Portuguese Maritime Spatial Plan covers the entire national maritime space, from the baselines to the outer limit of the continental shelf, integrating inland maritime waters, the territorial sea, the exclusive economic zone and the continental shelf, including beyond 200 nautical miles. This Plan promotes compatibility between competing uses or activities, with a view to contributing to a better economic use of the marine environment and minimising the impact of human activities on the marine environment. It is also the instrument that allows the attribution of a Permit for Private Use of the National Maritime Space.

Portuguese Sea planning was formally assumed by the Assembly of the Republic in 2014, through the Basic Law of the National Maritime Spatial Planning and Management Policy. This legal framework aims to manage the human activities that occur in the Portuguese sea, both in spatial and temporal terms, with a view to minimising conflicts, compatibility between activities and uses and the sustainable use of marine resources and services. According to the Basic Law for the Ordering and Management of the National Maritime Space, the Ordering of the National Maritime Space will be done through the preparation of the Situation Plan.

The National Maritime Space Planning Situation Plan (PSOEM) is the first instrument that organises the national maritime space, considering the territorial sea, the EEZ and the Continental Shelf up to its outer limit. The PSOEM thus makes an important

contribution to national cohesion, reinforcing the continent's connection to the archipelagos of Madeira and the Azores, consolidating the geopolitical component of the designated Portuguese Strategic Triangle, as a maritime centrality in the Atlantic basin.

The resolution of the Council of Ministers no. 203-A/2019 approved the National Maritime Space Planning Situation Plan. The concerns about the marine litter impacts are transversal to several sections from the PSOEM. According to Section 10C for the Territorial Sea and Maritime Inland Waters Activities, the management of maritime space must aim for the best use, exploring synergies and avoiding, or minimising, negative effects on other uses.

The 2001 UNESCO Convention on the Protection of Underwater Cultural Heritage, ratified in 2006 by Portugal reinforces national law to protect underwater cultural heritage in the EEZ and the Continental Shelf. Within the scope of scientific research activity in the field of underwater cultural heritage, projects that do not require maritime space reservation remain under the collection legal provisions of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea. In sections 11C/PCE and 13C, regarding the cultural and underwater heritage and sinking of ships and other structures, training, information and awareness-raising actions must also be developed with key stakeholders, aiming to create opportunities for cooperation with a view to the protection of underwater cultural heritage and increase cultural sensitivity and awareness of the community.

According to Good practices contained in sections 10C, 1C/CPE, and 13C the following practices must be considered (among others):

- Under no circumstances should this activity be the cause, intentional or negligent, of marine litter, and the materials used in the promotion and dissemination of routes and visits must be biodegradable;
- The practice of the activities must contribute to the good state of the marine environment, promoting the collection of marine litter that is deposited in places of interest, and must all later be transported to land and sent to an appropriate final destination to its typology.

Addressing ML often requires a multi-faceted approach, involving policy measures, technological solutions, public awareness campaigns, and international

collaboration. Maritime spatial planning provides an opportunity to integrate these measures into a comprehensive strategy for sustainable marine resource use.

The MSFD requires EU MS to take the necessary measures to achieve a good coastal and oceanic environmental status. In Portugal, the DGRM (General-Directorate for Natural Resources, Security and Maritime Services) is one of the national agencies in charge of implementing such measures. For MSFD, 11 Descriptors have been defined for monitoring the environmental status of the oceans in terms of marine biodiversity, eutrophication, contaminants, marine litter (Descriptor 10 (D10)), and submarine noise.

MSFD transposed into national law by Decree-Law No 108/2010, of 13 October in its current wording, establishes the community framework within the scope of the protection and conservation of the marine environment, and aims to achieve or maintain the GES of the marine environment. Each implementation cycle lasts for 6 years. The 1st cycle took place in the period between 2012 and 2018 and included the Preparation Phase and the Programme of Measures Phase. The 2nd cycle of the MSFD runs between 2018 and 2024.

During this last cycle, the updating of the initial reports was carried out with data collected between 2012 and 2018, following the methodological standards established by Commission Decision (EU) 2017/848, of 17 May, which revoked the previous Commission Decision 2010/477/EU, of 1 September. This new Decision introduced new criteria and standards, reducing the number of criteria that MS must monitor and evaluate, and subjecting the maintained criteria to a risk analysis approach, to make it easier for MS to focus their action on the main anthropogenic pressures that affect its marine waters. The relationship between the old criteria and indicators established in the 2010 Decision and the criteria of the new Decision for the D10, is presented in the following table (Table 1).

Table 1 - Relationship between the criteria established by Decision (EU) 2017/848 and the criteria and indicators established by Decision 2010/477/EU (P-Pressure; I-Impact) (adapted from MM, SRMCT, SRAAC 2020).

Descriptor	Decision Criteria 2017/848	Decision 2010/477 Criteria	P / I
D10	D10C1 - Composition, quantity and distribution of marine litter	Partially: 10.1, 10.1.1, 10.1.2	Pressure
	D10C2 - Composition, quantity and distribution of microscopic litter	Partially: 10.1,10.1.3	Pressure
	D10C3 - Amount of litter ingested	Partially: 10.1, 10.2.1	Pressure
	D10C4 - Negative effects of litter by species	10.2	Impact

Following the requirements of the MSFD, Portugal is monitoring and reporting the quantity and quality of plastic marine litter through national agencies and research institutions.

The implementation of the MSFD in Portugal is coordinated by the Directorate-General for Natural Resources, Safety and Maritime Services (DGRM), with Portuguese Institute of Sea and Atmosphere, (IPMA) responsible for the scientific component in the evaluation of the GES of marine waters, and the Directorate General for Sea Policy (DGPM) responsible for the economic and social analysis of the use of marine waters. In the Azores subdivision, the work was coordinated by the Regional Directorate for Marine Affairs (DRAM) and in the Madeira subdivision by the Regional Directorate for Spatial Planning and the Environment (DRAAC).

The national D10 technical group, created to develop specific methodologies in areas that require coordination at the community level, include several entities such as DGRM, IPMA and the Portuguese Environmental Agency (APA).

4.3 State of play in some other EU countries

In order to provide some elements regarding the state of consideration of ML-related issues in MSP plans of other EU countries, a questionnaire was prepared (Annex 1) and shared with some MSP experts across the EU. The purpose of such survey was purely exemplificatory, not claiming to be exhaustive or systematic. The questionnaire addressed the typology of the plan and its geographic scope and aimed to understand whether ML was considered at all as an issue to be addressed, and eventually what objectives and measures were identified by the plan and in relation to what maritime sectors. A number of experts from different countries were contacted: Belgium, Bulgaria, Finland, France, Ireland, Malta, Romania, Slovenia and Spain. This provided a broad coverage across all European regional seas. All contacted experts were responsive but not all of them participated in the survey, due to different considerations of opportunity and feasibility in the context of their national planning processes. The results from the survey formed the basis for the state of play described in this paragraph.

The survey revealed that some MSP plans across the EU do not take ML issues explicitly into consideration because this is considered out of the scope of MSP, as defined at the national level. For example, the **Spanish** national MSP plan just refers to ML in the objectives for MSP for the Region of Galicia. In this country, ML is addressed only through the MSFD process (Descriptor 10). Nonetheless, the MSFD and MSP processes in Spain are well linked, and the results from MSFD and some of the related monitoring programmes are used for the implementation of MSP. It means that, in the case of ML, some information regarding the monitoring programmes and the spatial distribution of litter will be used in the implementation of the MSP measures, for example, in measure OEM1 related to the spatial analysis of cumulative pressures arising from the spatial concentration of certain uses and activities.

The **Finnish** national MSP plan considers marine waters and a coastal strip. In fact, the plan covers the whole sea area of Finland, from the coastline and including territorial waters and the EEZ. The plan also examines the land-sea interactions, in close collaboration with the Coastal Strategy. The plan acknowledges the relevance of pollution and particularly of ML in its descriptive sections, such as in the description of nature conservation and management: *"Litter is a growing problem in the Baltic Sea. Litter ends up in the sea as a result of recreational use, boating and fishing, as well as from construction sites, wastewater treatment plant diversion and*

effluent. Most of the litter is plastic". Another example that also refers to the ML issue is provided in the section dedicated to the goals set for MSP regarding the marine environment: "*Maritime spatial planning and national land use planning can have an indirect positive impact on several descriptors of the good status of the marine environment. These include [...], increases in marine litter, etc.*". More directly, the plan addresses ML issues by setting objectives to improve waste management at ports and to improve recycling opportunities in marinas (smaller ports). Regarding circular economy in relation to ML pollution, the vision of the plan promotes resource-efficient and circular economy solutions for sustainable blue economy, but it does not specifically identify the ways in which the reuse/recycling would be implemented, or which marine sectors it would focus on.

The **Belgian** national MSP plan³ considers ML in the stocktaking phase and in the vision. ML is considered in the spatial analysis of the Belgian sea area (Annex 1, MSP 2020-2026) under the section "*Current environmental and natural state of the Belgian part of the North Sea*" and the subheading "*Pollution and disturbance in the Belgian part of the North Sea*". Pollution of the seafloor, the beaches and the water column is described, including ML. Shipping, fisheries and aquaculture are given as examples of maritime activities that can be a source of ML. Examples of ML are given such as discarded fishing nets and litter from land that reach the ocean via water streams or wind. Beach litter is also specified, and possible sources are listed such as fireworks and beach bars, as well as individual tourists. It is also mentioned that the "Fishing for Litter" project was relaunched, and that in 2017 the Action Plan Marine Litter was set up between different policy levels to enable a coordinated approach to tackle this issue. Possible negative effects of ML on organisms and on the ecosystem in general are described. A distinction is made between floating litter and litter on the seafloor, and for both, estimations are given on quantities, as well as composition (the majority being plastic litter). In addition, estimates are given on the presence of microplastics,

³ Royal Decree 22/05/2019 for the establishment of a marine spatial plan for the period from 2020-2026 for the Belgian sea areas

(https://etaamb.openjustice.be/nl/koninklijk-besluit-van-22-mei-2019_n2019013159.html)

Annex 1: Spatial analysis of the sea areas (<https://www.health.belgium.be/nl/bijlage-1-mrp-ruimtelijke-analyse-van-de-zeegebieden>)

Annex 2: Long-term vision, objectives and indicators, and spatial policy choices (<https://www.health.belgium.be/nl/bijlage-2-mrp-langetermijnvisie-doelstellingen-en-indicatoren-en-ruimtelijke-beleidskeuzes>)

as well as beach litter. Much more detail on the subject of ML is given in the current version of the MSP (2020-2026) compared to the previous one (2014-2020). In this plan, reference to ML is provided in the vision, where four core tasks are defined in the context of a policy direction towards 2050. One of the core tasks - "*An adaptive management requires adapted and transparent procedures*" - states the need for a reevaluation of the current Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) approach. A waste management plan was given as an example of how impacts could already be minimised at the design phase of a project. In addition, reference is made to the "polluter pays" principle (Annex 2, MSP 2020-2026).

The **Slovenian** MSP plan is developed at national level but it assigns certain tasks and responsibilities to municipalities too. This plan encompasses the marine domain of the territorial waters and a coastal terrestrial strip. The plan considers ML-related issues in a broad sense in the vision, where the spatial development of the sea and the coast addresses the importance of a good state/condition of the marine environment. Among the objectives of spatial planning, waste management, prevention of pollution of the sea and on the coast and, as a result, the good condition of the marine environment are identified. In terms of measures, the MSP plan MS specifies how to deal with ML for individual sectors. The plan targets sea-based related ML sources, linked to maritime activities by including prevention measures. In fact, no areas are identified in Slovenia needing ML pollution remediation. All tourism sub-sectors are targeted in general for ML pollution prevention, while aquaculture, shipping and ports are targeted more in detail by encouraging collection of waste from fishing activities (e.g. facilities in harbours to deliver old fishing nets) and from shipping (e.g. port reception facilities). ML pollution prevention is implemented in the country, regardless of the plan, and the awareness of the individual stakeholders is now at a fairly high level. A big issue is constituted by potential accidents at sea, due to the enormous number of cargo ships entering the Port of Koper.

In **Bulgaria**, the national MSP plan considered the sea domain and a terrestrial strip. This plan addresses ML issues in the stocktaking phase, as one of the issues of pollution to be solved through the provisions of the MSFD (Bulgarian Marine Strategy and Programme of Measures, i.e. implementation of Descriptor 10). ML is also considered in detail in the EIA Report supporting the MSP plan. Moreover, ML is considered (1) in the Specific objective 4.1. *Cooperation to reduce pollutant levels to*

values harmless to marine ecosystems, where one of the strategic measures is the significant reduction in the amount of waste entering or present in the sea through effective control of waste generation in the areas of the water area and territory of the Black Sea coast; (2) in the Specific objective 4.3. *Collaboration for shared services, jobs and products (based on the Common Maritime Agenda for the Black Sea)*, where one of the recommendations is focused on the improvement of the state of the marine environment and coordination of actions for addressing transboundary environmental challenges and reducing plastic ML. The specific objectives of the plan it is foreseen to “*reduce the levels of all types of pollutants to values that are not harmful to marine ecosystems through incident prevention, effective management of land-based sources of pollution and industrial activities in coastal areas and the shelf, including effective control and gradual restriction or sanctioning of the activity of objects outside the scope of the constructed sewage systems or without adequately functioning own treatment facilities, as well as introduction of innovative sanitary solutions within the borders of the beaches outside the concession area; Significant reduction of the amount of waste entering or present in the sea through effective control of the formation of waste in the sea and coastal areas*”. In the plan no specific measures related to ML are included. Rather, recommendations are provided (as mentioned above). The EIA of the Plan refers to the implementation of the MSFD and Programme of Measures (fully integrated into the plan). The ecological indicators for monitoring of the Plan are linked to the descriptors for assessing the impacts of the implemented measures from the Marine Strategy. Environmental indicators are linked in particular with Specific Objective 4.1, for the improvement of the ecological state of the Black Sea and reduction of pollution, in cooperation with other Black Sea countries. Both land-based and sea-based ML pollution is targeted by the plan with prevention measures targeting tourism, aquaculture, shipping, ports, as well as agriculture and coastal industries. The plan also considers improvements in waste management (general), collection of waste from fishing and shipping activities, awareness raising among professionals to prevent litter pollution, and restriction/reduction of certain activities/materials/products (e.g. types/materials of fishing gear, boxes). In relation to circular economy developments, the plan foresees for the aquaculture sector the development and introduction of regulations for the removal of abandoned installations for aquaculture and pond nets, in order to prevent pollution of the marine environment with solid waste and reduce the risk of accidents.

The **Irish** National Marine Planning Framework (NMPF) defines the overarching objectives, the context and the criteria for any given planning proposal at sea. For any given proposal a range of Overarching Marine Planning Policies (OMPPs) and Sectoral Marine Planning Policies (SMPPs) may need to be considered and applied to ensure full compliance with all relevant NMPF objectives and policies. OMPPs apply to all proposals capable of having impacts in the maritime area. OMPPs include policies aligned with the MSFD and its descriptors, including the “Marine Litter Policy 1”⁴. The “Marine litter policy 1” tests that *“Proposals that facilitate waste re-use or recycling, or that reduce marine and coastal litter will be supported, where they contribute to the policies and objectives of this NMPF. Proposals that could potentially increase the amount of litter that is discharged into the maritime area, either intentionally or accidentally, must include measures (such as development of a waste management plan) to, in order of preference and in accordance with legal requirements: a) avoid, b) minimise, or c) mitigate the litter. Demonstration of these measures must provide satisfactory evidence that the proposal is able to manage all waste without creation of litter”*. The “Marine Litter Policy 1”, concerns any sector and any proposal that may impact or be impacted with/by marine litter. It is also mentioned that *“All maritime activity should be undertaken in such a manner as to reduce the likelihood of marine litter generation”*. Waste management, prevention of loss of items into the marine environment, reuse of materials and increased recyclability are required as key considerations of any maritime activity. The Programme for Government commits to aggressively tackle the issue of waste, ghost nets and illegal dumping in the marine environment through rigorous implementation of the Port Reception Facilities Directives and by requiring all Irish fishing trawlers to participate in the Clean Oceans Initiative and the related OSPAR area Fishing For Litter programme, ensuring that litter fished up at sea is brought ashore.

⁴ The corresponding Irish Marine Strategy environmental targets (2020) for marine litter are:

- D10T1a: The composition, amount and spatial distribution of litter in the coastline, and on the seabed, are at levels that do not cause harm to the coastal or marine environment;
- D10T1b: In accordance with the provisions of Article 5 of Directive (EU) 2019/904 by year-end 2023 eliminate beach litter caused by the items prohibited from the market under that Directive. These items are: plastic cotton bud sticks, disposable plastic cutlery and plates, plastic straws, plastic beverage stirrers, plastic balloon sticks, expandable polystyrene fast food containers and expandable polystyrene beverage containers and cups.

The recently approved **Romanian** MSP plan, which considers the sea space and a coastal terrestrial strip, includes ML as part of the specific objective concerning waste management, marine pollution and MSFD objectives (achieving the good ecological status of the Black Sea marine region). The plan targets both land-based and sea-based sources, by particularly addressing tourism, shipping, ports, industry and urban sources. The plan tackles Improvements in waste management (general), and encourages collection of waste from fishing activities (e.g. facilities in harbours to deliver old fishing nets) and collection of waste from shipping (e.g. port reception facilities). The plan also refers to initiatives for floating litter removal.

5 Marine litter pollution and its relevance for the maritime sectors

This chapter summarises some essential knowledge elements regarding the origin of ML pollution and its effects on the activities undertaken at sea. The purpose is to provide to marine planners and decision makers, as well as to maritime sector representatives, a practically accessible synthesis on the topic which is well covered by a very large and ever-growing number of research articles, technical reports and policy papers. In the following paragraphs, two main elements are addressed: ML sources and ML impacts. Some general knowledge elements derived from updated literature are reported. In addition to that, with the aim of providing concrete examples in relation to specific territories, a focus on these topics is provided on the two demo sites considered by the MAELSTROM project.

5.1 Sources of marine litter

ML can originate from multiple sources. It is generally recognised that most litter found at sea originates from land-based sources, where is either dumped or discarded at coastlines or transported into the sea via wind, runoff, sewage outlets and rivers from more inland areas. However, litter can also be directly discarded, lost or abandoned at the sea by fisheries, shipping and other maritime activities. These are the so-called sea-based sources and, even if they tend to be relatively less important than terrestrial sources, in some areas, this type of ML can be substantial with serious impacts on populations, ecosystems and economic sectors (see section 5.2).

Several terrestrial sources of ML have been fully recognized. Public waste is dumped (intentionally or inadvertently) on the beach, coast or rivers, and enters the marine environment. Tourists and recreational visitors are a key source of this type of litter. Poor waste management practices can be another cause of ML dispersal in the environment: collection, transport and disposal phases are crucial. Poorly managed coastal and river landfills, waterways, as well as inefficient transportation, are important sources of ML. Industrial products can enter the marine environment when they are inappropriately wasted or lost by mistake during transportation, on land and at sea. This includes for example raw material (pellets) for plastic production that is often discovered during plastic monitoring investigations of marine waste (see e.g. Karlsson et al. 2018). Sewage Related Debris (SRD) is a consequence of the release of

untreated wastewater into the marine environment, due to the absence of waste treatment plants or combined sewer overflows during storm events. Stormwater drains are also a source of ML because waste can accumulate in storm drains and subsequently be discharged into the marine environment during storm events.

Waste can also be produced at sea, generated by maritime activities. The fishing industry contributes to the loss or deliberate dumping of nets, ropes and other fishing gears. Shipping is also an important source: although international legislation prohibits the disposal of waste artefacts in the sea, these are still inadvertently dumped, inappropriately stored or intentionally released by ships. One of the main problems detected is the recurring loss of containers transported with commercial purposes. In 2022, 661 were reported to be lost at sea. Considering the fifteen-year period surveyed (2008-2022), on average 1,566 containers were lost at sea each year (World Shipping Council, 2023)⁵. Tourism and the recreational industry also represent a relevant source of ML on the beaches and at sea. Owners and operators of recreational boats throw away, unintentionally or deliberately, waste and other manufactured items in the marine environment, such as food containers, plastic bottles and recreational fishing gears. Offshore oil and gas exploration and exploitation can result in the accidental and intentional discharge of a number of items in the marine environment such as gloves and helmets, as well as waste generated by exploration and resources extraction.

5.1.1 Demo site 1: lagoon of Venice (IT)

The lagoon of Venice and its coastal waters are expected to receive input of waste from both land-based and sea-based sources. Up to now, no studies are available to quantify the entity of this pollution pressure. The features of both the drainage basin and the coastal waters, as well as the human activities they host, are key to understanding the possible sources of ML in the area.

The watershed of the lagoon of Venice has a total extension of 2038 km², about 1/9 of the Veneto region's overall surface (Figure 1). The territory is divided into 108 municipalities. The watershed is divided into several sub-basins (Figure 1b) that drain into the lagoon. The watershed also includes a separate area (the canal Vela

⁵ <https://www.worldshipping.org/news/world-shipping-council-releases-containers-lost-at-sea-report-2023-update>

hydrographic basin), which drains directly into the lagoon without receiving any other water contribution along its course.

a)

b)

Figure 1. a) the watershed of the Venice lagoon in the territory of Veneto region; b) the sub-basins within the watershed territory. Source: Regione del Veneto, 2023⁶.

The hydrographic network is quite articulated, as illustrated in Figure 2.

⁶ <https://sistemavenezia.regione.veneto.it/content/bacino-scolante-nella-laguna-di-venezia>

Figure 2. The hydrographic network of the drainage basin of the lagoon of Venice. Source: Regione del Veneto, 2023.

In terms of human activities, the prevalent land use is agriculture, accounting for 77% of the land cover, lagoon waters (about 11%) and urban areas (6.2%) (Figure 3). Most frequent cultivations are cereals (corn), soya and sugar beet and horticulture (often in mobile greenhouses) in some specialised and localised areas near coastal areas.

Figure 3. Land use in the watershed of the Venice lagoon. Source: Regione del Veneto, 2023⁷.

Industrial activities are also undertaken in the drainage basin. Energy production facilities, including power plants, are present in the area, contributing to the energy needs of the Veneto region and beyond. The manufacturing industry includes the production of glass, ceramics, textiles, etc. Food industry is also present, including seafood products. Shipbuilding is very important: shipyards in the region are involved in constructing and repairing various types of vessels, contributing to both local employment and the maritime economy. Tourism is by large the most important economic activity, with many tourism operators, hotels, restaurants and recreational activities, present in the catchment area of the Venice lagoon. The major port of Venice, Porto Marghera, is situated within the lagoon's watershed. This port is a hub for various industrial activities, including the import and export of goods. It serves as an important transportation link for industries in the region. The industrial zone of Porto Marghera is still an important industrial area. After the sharp decrease in the

⁷ <https://www.regione.veneto.it/web/ambiente-e-territorio/bacino-scolante>

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production of petrochemical products, which made the history of the area, Porto Marghera has now switched to green chemistry, still producing plastics in a more sustainable way, and other industrial materials.

Maritime activities such as maritime traffic, fisheries, aquaculture, and coastal tourism represent sea-based ML pollution sources for the area. In fact, the Gulf of Venice is characterised by intense maritime traffic from merchant ships, ferries and recreational crafts. Accumulation of fishing gears in the rocky outcrops and its surroundings (Moschino et al., 2019) have demonstrated the relevance of the fishing sector as a pollution source of ML. Aquaculture activities are widespread in the area, particularly mussel farming. Aquaculture nets are among the most frequent waste types found along the Venice littorals.

A study undertaken in the framework of the MAELSTROM project (Deliverable D2.1, 2012) showed that the main source for beach litter as derived from EMODnet database and other records is related to public activities (domestic and touristic waste), the second category is represented by litter waste whose source is not identifiable and then fishing-related litter.

Results of the Fishing for Litter project activities undertaken in the north western Adriatic Sea by Pasanisi et al. (2023), which also included the area of the MAELSTROM demo site, show that land-based sources are predominant in terms of the number of items (41%), whereas sea-based sources prevailed in terms of weight (57%). Most of the collected ML was attributed to packaging-related use, both in terms of item number (47%) and weight (29%) of the total sample. On the other hand, when focusing on identifiable sources of ML, sea-based activities (fishing, aquaculture, fly-tipping and shipping) predominated in both studied areas (Chioggia and Civitanova Marche) in terms of weight, probably due to the relatively long distance from the coast (20 km on average). Additionally, in Chioggia, sea-based sources predominated also in the number of items, due to the frequency and abundance of fishing-related items.

Venice is known for its narrow streets running adjacent to a system of canals, making it easy for plastics and other litter to enter the waterways and damage the marine ecosystem. Despite less than 50,000 residents living in the historical centre, the island city is also a temporary home to a massive number of tourists. The latest official data note that, prior to the COVID-19 lockdowns, Venice recorded the presence of over 37 million tourists throughout the year. The statistics show a clear case of increasing overtourism, resulting in litter amounts rising to perilous heights during the peak

tourist season. The effect of tourism has also been exhibited in recent joint research ventures of Venice Lagoon Plastic Free (VLPF) with the Chemistry Department of the Institute Montani of Fermo. A sampling study conducted after the sudden stop in tourism due to travel restrictions showed a significant drop in microcontaminants found in the canals. This means that tourism brings unfortunate after-effects regarding not only our regular perceptions of litter, but also litter that may not be visible to the naked eye. In March 2021, the City of Venice formally joined the international WWF policy-oriented programme Plastic Smart Cities. The city's inclusion in this programme implies the elaboration and, most importantly, the implementation of an inclusive strategy and its execution plan to prevent the production of plastic waste and enhance its management with circular solutions, compounded with the monitoring of progress achieved with annual baselines and measurable targets.

5.1.2 Demo site 2: Ave river estuary (PT)

Portugal has a high dependence on coastal activities and is susceptible to the impacts of ML due to the various demographic pressures on coastal, estuarine, and riparian areas. Litter pollution is influenced by local, regional, and global land-based or sea-based sources (Prata et al., 2020). The land-based sources are considered the main sources of ML in densely populated coastal areas (Andrady et al., 2011). Since water courses are the most frequent eco receptor for all groups (Vieira et al., 2007), this environment is more susceptible to litter contamination (Prata et al., 2020). However, sea-based sources of litter pollution can be also important and include touristic activities, commercial fishing, and shipping (Prata et al., 2020). Addressing ML in Portugal requires a comprehensive approach involving waste management improvements, public awareness campaigns, policy interventions, and international cooperation to mitigate the various sources and impacts of this type of pollution. Efforts to reduce plastic production and use, encourage positive consumer behaviour, improve waste collection and disposal infrastructure, and promote responsible tourism practices are all essential components of any effective strategy to combat ML in Portuguese waters.

Located in the northwest of Portugal, the Ave River hydrological basin has an approximate area of 1390 km². From its source in Serra da Cabreira to its mouth in Vila do Conde, its main river length is 101 km and its average flow at the mouth is 40 m³ /s (Rocha et al., 2019). The Ave River estuarine area is located in the Vila do Conde

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municipality, in the district of Porto. The municipality is limited to the north by the municipality of Póvoa de Varzim, to the east by Vila Nova de Famalicão and Trofa, to the south by Maia and Matosinhos and to the west it has a coastline on the Atlantic Ocean (Figure 4)

The River Ave differs from other northern Portuguese rivers not only because of its high pollution density but also due to the large spatial and temporal variability of pollutants concentration (Gonçalves and Alpuim, 2011; Rocha et al., 2019). During the last years, several monitoring works have been developed to assess the anthropogenic pollution in the Ave River and estuary, including emerging contaminants (e.g. Ribeiro et al., 2016; Caetano et al., 2016; Couto et al., 2018, 2019; Rocha et al., 2019, Montes et al., 2023).

Overall, the watercourses of the Ave hydrographic basin are exposed to serious disturbances, regarding physical, chemical, and biological levels, with few exceptions recorded only in the upstream area, close to the springs. These disturbances translate into several effects in the ecosystem, namely the degradation of the riparian curtain, the alteration of the channel, and the poor quality of the water, with significant consequences on the aquatic communities. The surrounding area of the estuary of the Ave river is characterised by a small wasteland with a few species of ruderal plants and very low fauna densities, focused on the left margin.

The information on the presence and categorization of marine litter on the Ave hydrographic basin is very limited. According to González-Fernández et al. (2021) the Ave River basin annual floating litter loading is approximately 87,306 items. Together with MAELSTROM ecological assessment campaigns, this research represents the only works performed so far on floating macrolitter in the Ave River basin. Deliverable 2.3 within the MAELSTROM project explores the “ecosystem status and pollution assessment of the demo sites in Venice and Porto”. Hydrological processes were measured and modelled, and water column microplastics and surface macroplastics were sampled along with water quality and ecological status monitoring. Repeated sampling campaigns will continue in early 2024 following the implementation of the Bubble Barrier Vila do Conde. Not only this will serve to assess and validate the technology but will also to add information to the crucial collection of ML data in Portugal and in the northeast Atlantic. Furthermore, the co-operative involvement of the Vila do Conde municipality and the integral network of regional stakeholders can inform ML remediation policies and spatial planning guidance.

An analysis conducted under the activities of the MAELSTROM project, which analysed the characteristics of the ML found in the Portuguese beaches using the EMODnet database (Iglesias et al., 2023), revealed that, for the municipality of Póvoa de Varzim, northern of the Ave estuary, the litter found in the beaches was 86% of plastics, 4% of glass, 3% of metal, wood and paper and 1% of clothes. Regarding sources, 51% of the found litter was classified as public litter, 18% non-sourced, 14% sewage-related, 10% for fishing and 6% for shipping.

It was mentioned by other authors that fishing-related litter can indicate deposition by the sea from fishing grounds because it is not expected to be disposed of directly on beaches but rather at sea or at fishing docks (Prevenios et al., 2018). In Portugal, local/artisanal fishing, also called polyvalent fishing, is the main fishing gear along the whole coastal region, including in the Azores archipelago (Lloret et al., 2018; INE, 2022). The fishing gear used is diverse but mainly comprises lines and nets. The vessels used for this polyvalent fishing represent around 80 % of the total fishing vessels in Portugal, with a considerable number of non-motorized vessels (INE, 2022). It is important to notice that the vessels for local fishing cannot go beyond the area of the captaincy to which they are attached, and they cannot navigate beyond the 6 miles. Therefore, the fishing-related items recorded on beaches likely originate from these near-shore activities.

Along the hydrographic basin of Ave River, several pressures are identified as being able to contribute to the occurrence of litter in the aquatic ecosystem (Figure 4). Agriculture is a significant source of debris in Ave River since around 31% of the hydrographic basin is covered by agriculture. This region is one of the most industrialised areas of Portugal, supporting a huge number of industries, such as those of textiles (18 Installations covered by the IPPC regime - Integrated Pollution Prevention and Control) and surface treatment (electrolytic or chemical process; 11 with environmental licence-IPPC), metal plating, leather tanning, rubber and plastic, cutlery and metalworking manufacturers (Rocha et al., 2019, Figure 5). These pressures result in high levels of pollution and decrease of water quality that have been registered in this region during the last decades (Couto et al., 2019). Other activities also contribute to the impact of marine litter in the aquatic ecosystem, such as landfills (5 plants: Urban solid waste and Nonhazardous industrial waste), aquaculture plants (5 installations), port facilities (4 ports in the transitional waters area), and tourism. The latter is more pronounced in Ave estuary, due to the needs

and impacts of communities which avail of the local resources, both attracting tourists and hosting a significant and engaged fishing industry in both riverine and coastal areas. The city of Vila do Conde sits on the northern bank of the Ave River estuary and hosts a considerable hub of industry, fishing, tourism, and recreation. It is recognized as one of the country's primary and most sought-after bathing destinations. The city is part of the same urban conglomeration as Póvoa de Varzim, together forming an urban cluster with 100,000 inhabitants, ranking as the seventh largest in Portugal and the third largest in the Northern region. Villa do Conde is an important region in both urban and rural dimensions and, through its progressive policies on environmental and socio-economic development, it acts as a crucial role model for neighbouring municipalities in the North of Portugal.

Figure 4. Ave River hydrographic basin location, Ave River estuary, and the main activities of land occupation in the region.

Figure 5. Ave River hydrographic basin and the location and classification of the main pollution sources.

As a constituent of the Porto Metropolitan Area subregion, the Municipality of Vila do Conde encompasses a total area of 149.03 km², recorded 80,921 inhabitants in 2021, and exhibits a population density of 543 inhabitants per km². The municipality is divided into 21 parishes, six of which extend along the coastline. This coastal positioning establishes a strong connection to the sea and maritime activities, significantly influencing the local economy and the development of a distinctive cultural identity. Recognizing the escalating global and local environmental challenges, the Municipal Council has adopted a strategy aimed at enhancing its marine resources and preserving the natural and scenic values of the territory.

Due to its extensive coastline, spanning approximately 16 km, and the intricate river network traversing the municipality's area, the Municipal Council of Vila do Conde (CMVC) has placed special emphasis on addressing aquatic pollution, investing more than half a million euros in environment protection (environmental education, nature and biodiversity protection).

With a special dedicated investment for (approximately 6 months, the Municipality contracted services which cost in excess of €20,000 after each clean-up, with an average amount of litter collected higher than 300,000 Kg per year⁸. In this context, the CMVC has been actively involved in developing and supporting projects addressing the issue of ML from a circular perspective. These initiatives encompass artistic endeavours to raise awareness about maritime pollution, as well as to initiatives to explore innovative technologies and business models for the recovery of plastics and marine waste. The municipality of Vila do Conde is taking a proactive approach to tackling marine litter by partnering with the MAELSTROM team to co-design and implement a Bubble Barrier in the Ave River estuary, also co-promoting litter prevention and remediation policies, towards an effective and sustainable blue circular economy. Such examples of multi-stakeholder collaboration and engaged co-design and co-ownership, build not only trust and innovation adoption but also allow for a pathway to science-backed policy decisions that support ML reduction, reuse, and recycling.

5.2 The Impact of marine litter on maritime and coastal activities

The impacts of ML, including microplastics, are wide and varied and many are still poorly quantified. ML can have detrimental implications for marine species, habitats, and ecosystems, as well as on maritime sectors and coastal economies, and even pose a risk to human health.

Marine organisms can get entangled and trapped on abandoned, lost or otherwise discarded fishing gear (ALDFG) or ingest plastic litter, which can lead to poor physiological condition, death or severe suffering (Werner et al., 2016). Ingestion of plastic particles by commercial species has also been widely reported (Savoca et al., 2021). Furthermore, ML can serve as a vector of contaminants, microbes and invasive species, with risks to ecosystems and human health (Werner et al., 2016; Gunaalan et al., 2020; Vethaak and Legler, 2021).

Vital economic sectors such as coastal tourism and fisheries can be significantly affected by ML, and managing and reducing these impacts is often costly. Beach cleaning activities, citizen science initiatives, and local action groups are common practice in European bathing sites, a financial burden that usually falls on coastal

⁸ All presented economical estimates are preliminary data, resulting from the iterations with authorised representatives of the Municipality. Such estimates will be updated and finalised within the completion of the MAELSTROM project.

municipalities, NGOs, or volunteers. The productivity, viability, profitability and safety of the fishing and aquaculture industries are highly vulnerable to the impacts of ML (UNEP, 2021). Annual costs to the European fishing industry due to damage and losses in revenue have been estimated to reach €61.7 million (Acoleyen et al., 2013), while the total costs associated with damaged vessels and equipment have been estimated to be between €1.5 and €4 million per year to the Dutch shipping fleet (Werner et al., 2016). Table 2 below provides some information on estimated costs undertaken by different economic sectors to reduce and manage impacts from ML in Europe.

Table 2 - Estimated annual costs of ML impacts on maritime and coastal sectors in Europe

Economic sector	Impact/action	Estimated annual costs (€)	Country/Region	Source
Coastal tourism	Reduced aesthetics - beach litter removal and disposal costs	€ 216,920 per municipality	Adriatic-Ionian	Vlachogianni, 2017
		€ 176,000 per municipality	Netherlands	Ecorys, 2012 <i>in</i> Werner et al., 2016
		€ 200,000/municipality	Belgium	Mouat et al. 2010
Fishing	Damage/repair of nets, loss in revenue due to smaller catch	€ 5,378 per fishing vessel € 3,542 per fishing vessel	Adriatic-Ionian EU seas	Vlachogianni, 2017 UN Environment, 2017
Aquaculture	Damage/repair of equipment	€ 3,228 per aquaculture farm unit	Adriatic-Ionian	Vlachogianni, 2017
Shipping	Damage/repair propellers, vessels	\$2..95 billions	APEC	Mcllgorm et al., 2022
Harbours & marinas	Litter removal	€ 8,000 per harbour	United Kingdom	Mouat et al., 2010
	Litter removal and disposal	€ 8,518 per harbour	Adriatic-Ionian	Vlachogianni, 2017
Ports	Floating litter removal	€ 300,000 per port	Spain (Port of Barcelona)	Werner et al., 2016
	Litter removal	€ 8,035 per port	United Kingdom	Mouat et al., 2010

Economic sector	Impact/action	Estimated annual costs (€)	Country/Region	Source
	Litter removal	€ 61,015 per port	Spain	Werner et al., 2016

Insights about the impact on fisheries

Direct costs incurred by the fishing sector arise from the need to repair or replace gear that has been damaged or lost due to encounters with ML; repairing boats with tangled propellers, anchors, rudders, clogged intake hoses, etc.; loss of earnings due to time spent separating fishery products from marine waste; loss of earnings from reduced or contaminated catches resulting from encounters with ML, including ghost fishing (Newman et al., 2015). Furthermore, fisheries also suffer indirect income losses due to the effect of loss and abandonment of fishing gear on fish stocks (MacFayden et al., 2009 cited in Newman et al., 2015).

Derelict fishing gear (DFG) comprises a large proportion of ML and can cause economic losses to fisheries. DFG includes any equipment capable of capturing fish and shellfish lost from fisheries, including trawls, gillnets, traps, cages, and pots (National Research Council 2008).

The spread of recreational fishing in recent years has created an exponential growth in such ghost gears, which has a heavy impact on professional fishing.

Fisheries bear costs firstly due to the need to replace fishing gear lost at sea (as well as monitoring, cleaning and disposal costs) and secondly due to the reduction of potential harvestable catches of commercial and non-commercial species, thus decreasing the actual sustainability of that catch (Newman et al., 2015).

Mouat et al. (2010) calculated the direct economic impact of ML on Scottish fishing vessels (i.e. the costs of repairs and direct loss of earnings, not indirect losses due to ghost fishing), and estimated that, on average, ML costs for each fishing vessel are between 17,000 and 19,000 €/year. The time lost to eliminate waste from the networks represents a large part of this cost (12,000 €/year). Overall, ML costs for the Scottish fishing sector are between € 11.7 and € 13 million each year (Mouat et al., 2010). Therefore, ML reduces the total annual income of fleets by 5%. This is clearly a significant cost for a business that is already under great pressure and is so important for coastal communities.

Insights about the impact on beach tourism

The visible presence of ML has an impact on the aesthetic value and attractiveness of beaches. The presence of litter also affects recreational activities such as diving and snorkelling, and creates injuries to the propellers and jet intakes of recreational boaters. ML can thus discourage visitors from going to certain beaches. Reduced numbers of coastal visitors leads to lost revenues for the tourism sector, which in turn leads to a loss of revenue and jobs in the local and regional economy. The cost of clean-up activities associated with littering generally falls on local actors such as municipalities or private actors such as beach managers and hotel owners.

Insights about the impact on shipping

ML poses risk to shipping and transport vessels. Lost freight containers that float on or below the surface are a navigational risk to coastal and ocean shipping (McIlgorm, 2022). DFG poses an entanglement threat, especially to smaller vessels. Water intakes for engine cooling systems can clog with plastic waste, entanglement with ropes can cause propeller damage and even sinking of vessels (influx of seawater by stern tube) (McIlgorm, 2022). There are records of wrecked propeller shafts, stern gear and flexible couplings on engines, putting vessels out of operation, resulting in economic losses and risk of injury during repair operations (McIlgorm, 2022).

5.2.1 Demo site 1: Lagoon of Venice (IT)

The Venice lagoon is a Special Protection Area (IT3250046, 79/409/CEE, DGP n. 441/2007) and it comprises two Sites of Community Importance (IT3250030 and IT3250031). Outside of the lagoon, in the North-western Adriatic Sea rocky outcrops can be found. Two of them, located in front of the towns of Chioggia and Caorle (within the metropolitan city of Venice), are recognized as Sites of Community Importance (SCI) ("IT3250047 - Tegnue di Chioggia"; "IT3250048 - Tegnue di Porto Falconera"). The entire area and its MPAs are impacted by marine litter in several ways (Pasquini et al., 2016; Liubartseva et al., 2016, Liubartseva et al., 2018). Fisheries and tourism are of particular relevance because they are sources of ML and, at the same time, impacted by ML pollution.

Impact on fisheries

The impact of ML on fishing activities in the demo site can be illustrated by the results of the research conducted by Pasanisi et al. (2023). The sampling of ML accidentally caught by fishing nets was performed onboard during the fishing activity of 10 trawling vessels, 4 belonging to Chioggia (demo site area) and 6 to Civitanova Marche fishing fleets, operating with two different gears: bottom beam trawl/toothed dredges (TBB) and bottom otter trawl (OTB) (Pasanisi et al., 2023). As highlighted by the results illustrated in Table 3, the percentage of occurrence of ML in hauls is huge and the quantities of litter recorded are relevant.

Table 3. Percentage of hauls where at least one ML item was found and amounts of litter collected and analysed for area and type of fishing gear (from Pasanisi et al., 2023).

Study area	ML occurrence (% of hauls)	Weight (kg)	N. item s
Chioggia	-	257	1452
OTB	77	41	255
TBB	100	216	1197
Civitanova Marche	-	373	2641
OTB	99	373	2641
Total	-	630	4093

Values in bold indicate the total amount of ML collected in each study area and in total

In the framework of the same study, fish species were analysed and the presence of plastic in the gastro-intestinal tracts was quantified (Giani et al., 2020). On average, 2 fish out of 10 had ingested from one to five microplastics. The pelagic species (anchovy and pilchard) had the highest percentage of occurrence of ingested microplastics. Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and Polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs) were also measured in the muscle of fish species as well as biomarker responses. The results show negligible effects related to plastic ingestion by fish as well as low levels of contaminant accumulation in fish with microplastics in their gastro-intestinal tract.

Finally, impacts on fishing activities were also highlighted through interviews with sector operators. The following main impacts have been identified: damage to fishing equipment, lost fishing hours, risks to navigation and the safety of the crew. The majority of fishermen highlight waste management and storage problems on board fishing vessels (more than 41%), a slowdown in collection and separation activities

from the catch (around 27%), as well as the lack of suitable points for the disposal/land disposal (about 12%).

With the approval and definitive publication of the Italian “Salva Mare” Law (Law 17 May 2022, n. 60: *Provisions for the recovery of waste at sea and inland waters and for the promotion of the circular economy*), a regulatory framework for all activities that aim to protect the sea from waste in general and from plastic in particular has become available. In fact, the law recognizes the waste accidentally caught or voluntarily collected at sea, lakes, rivers and lagoons, including through cleaning campaigns, to that produced by ships, which can therefore be delivered separately, and free of charge, to port reception facilities. It will be up to the territorially competent municipalities for the management of urban waste to set up areas near the moorings if the mooring is outside the areas of competence of the Port System Authority.

The law also has other important objectives: (i) promote the recycling of plastic and other materials collected by fishermen; (ii) plan for the installation of devices and collection systems at the mouths of the rivers to intercept plastic before it reaches the sea; (iii) include environmental education activities for students, with the aim of promoting correct waste disposal practices and the recovery and reuse of goods and products at the end of the cycle, also with reference to the reduction of the use of plastic and available reuse systems; and (iv) adopt reward measures to encourage the collection of waste by fishing vessel commanders. Fish entrepreneurs who use materials with a reduced environmental impact and/or participate in cleaning campaigns and/or dispose of accidentally caught waste may be awarded environmental recognition, which certifies their commitment to respecting the environment and the sustainability of the fishing activities. Finally, cleaning campaigns may be started on the initiative of the Municipalities and other promoters, including the managing bodies of protected areas, environmental associations, those of sport and recreational fishermen, professional ones as well as managers of bathing establishments, NGOs, etc.

From 13 June 2018, with the approval of Council resolution no. 199, the Municipality of Venice had already implemented measures to prevent the abandonment of fishing equipment at sea and in the lagoon through the assimilation of special waste to urban waste. A specific collection service dedicated exclusively to fishermen was set up for fishing nets, mussel nets, ropes, lines, pots, etc. However, the municipal

provision was superseded and therefore implicitly cancelled by Legislative Decree 116/2020. From 1 January 2023 it will no longer be possible to assimilate special waste produced by fishing activities to municipal waste.

Impact on coastal tourism and recreational activities

An economic assessment of the costs of beach cleaning undertaken by the beach concessionaires in the area is not available. In addition to the costs of the personnel and the dedicated machinery, the disposal costs should be considered, being beach litter considered special waste. With the publication of the Italian "Salva Mare" Law (Law 17 May 2022, n. 60) mentioned before, wooden litter can now be considered as "biomass" and as such disposed but most importantly utilised for energy production.

In this demo site, waste deposited in the canals within and around the city of Venice represents an impact on daily life and tourism activities too. The Municipality of Venice regularly organises clean-up activities in the canals with the support of sector organisations and NGOs. For example, in a cleaning campaign organised in December 2023 with the participation of the association of gondoliers, 550kg of waste have been removed.

Impact on protected natural areas and valuable ecosystems

Along the north-western Adriatic Sea inner shelf, between 10 and 40 m depths, rocky crops rise up to 3–4 m above the bottom sediment. Their presence has been well-known since the 18th century and their exact locations have been identified through time by fishermen attracted by their fishing value and also because they represent a potential threat for bottom trawling. These rocky buildups, according to the traditions of the local fishermen, are known under various dialectal names, e.g., *tegnùe*, *trezze*, *pressure*, *lastrure*, *grèbeni* (Tosi et al. 2017).

In the environmental context of the north-western Adriatic Sea, with a seabed characterised by mobile sediment, the presence of these rocky substrates acts as an anchoring point for various sessile organisms. Encrusting algae, sponges, anemones, sedentary polychaetes, and corals are the sessile organisms that populate the *tegnùe*, where urchins, stars, ophiuras, hermit crabs, lobsters and small benthic fish find protection and shelter. All these organisms in turn represent a rich and varied food supply, which attracts the fish fauna that transits the Adriatic, such as sea bass and schools of cod in search of food and shelter. The fish species that populate the *tegnùe* are numerous: thrushes, blennies, damselfishes, sacs, scorpion fish, conger

eels and valuable fish species such as croakers and sea breams (see e.g. Gianni et al., 2023; Nesto et al., 2020; Curiel et al., 2017; Molin et al., 2011).

In the Mediterranean Sea the *tegnùe* represent a unique environment due to its structure and morphology. In addition, they favour both an increase in diversity in the animal and plant populations of the seabed and an increase in valuable fish species. For this reason, the Veneto Region, with its determination DGR 220 01/03/2011, has identified two Sites of Community Importance (SCIs): SCI "IT3250047 - Tegnùe di Chioggia" and SCI "IT3250048 - Tegnùe di Porto Falconera".

The impacts of ML on these important benthic habitats is evident. In fact, fishing gear such as nets, ropes, traps, floaters and leads, which are accidentally lost or discarded into the sea (ALDFG), can have an impact on the physical environment with subsequent alterations of marine habitats. In the Venice demo site such impact has been studied: rocky outcrops offshore of the Venice littoral were assessed for ghost net presence in the framework of the Ghost project. Over the 20 km² of area surveyed, 50% were interested by ALDFG, with a total of 347 gears marked (Figure 6). A total of 514 kg of fishing and aquaculture gears were removed from selected zones where the recovery of the benthic community was monitored. Study areas showed a statistically significant increase in the biodiversity indexes (Richness, Shannon, Margalef) of the communities considered (Da Ros et al., 2016).

Figure 6. Most probably ALDFG affected areas (Da Ros et al., 2016).

Tonin (2018; 2019) assessed the economic value of marine biodiversity improvement in coralligenous habitat through a contingent valuation survey administered to a sample of 4000 Italians. Households' willingness to pay (WTP) for biodiversity restoration and conservation ranges between €10.30 and €64.02 depending on the assumptions underlying the different models. The author also found that the main positive and significant determinants of WTP are a previous knowledge or familiarity with coralligenous habitats and biodiversity issues, income, education, environmental attitudes, and the knowledge that indiscriminate fishing may be dangerous for biodiversity in a coralligenous habitat. The study has proved that aggregate benefits related to the improvement of biodiversity as a result of restoration and conservation activities are significantly higher in comparison to the estimated costs of these activities.

5.2.2 Demo site 2: Ave river estuary (PT)

Since 2009, the Ave River hydrological basin has been monitored for its ecological status in compliance with the WFD. This assessment has been made in three monitoring cycles, from 2009 - 2015, 2016 - 2021, and now in 2022 - 2027. The ecological assessment revealed a notable degradation of the ecosystem status, particularly in

the Ave River estuary with the latest monitoring cycle describing the worst classification status to date ("Bad" during 2022 - 2027). This degradation in ecological status is believed to be associated with the increase of anthropogenic pressures, such as population increase, urban development, tourism, and recreation activities. The entire hydrographic basin has also experienced an increase in industrial activities, which can influence water quality and ecosystem health. Furthermore, a considerable threat to the environmental status is the decrease in freshwater fluxes due to climate change. Changes in river flow will produce alterations in the circulation, salinity, mixing of the water masses, and sedimentation patterns of the estuarine waters, as well as in nutrient delivery, primary production, the residence time of the water masses, oxygenation, stratification and other issues associated with stagnancy, and so affecting the environmental conditions (Canuel et al., 2012). In addition to the river flow, the estuarine regions can also experience the effects of the sea level rise (SLR), which will cause an increased salt-wedge penetration in the estuarine regions, the retention of sediments in the lower river courses and an expansion of some marine habitats, whereas others may wane (Iglesias et al., 2022). These patterns have been observed in other Portuguese estuaries, however, a lack in recent data for Ave River estuary reduced capacity to detect such effects.

Visual monitoring results indicated that the Ave River estuary has considerable contamination by macrolitter, most notably from styrofoam, plastic bags, and plastic bottles, which indicate a predominance of land-based public litter sources. This assessment determined an average frequency of 19.1 and 16.3 floating items per hour during Spring 2021 and Autumn 2021 campaigns, respectively. The highest percentage (aprox. 99%) of microplastic particles collected were <5 mm, with more than 40% between 0.100 and 0.500 μm . The study revealed the predominant characterised particles were plastic fragments and microfibrils. The prevalent size of microplastics detected in this survey was between 0.1 and 0.5 μm . This size class is considered to be bioavailable via active or passive ingestion. Microplastic ingestion has the potential to impact a wide range of organisms as they overlap with the size range of their prey, including zooplankton and ichthyoplankton, with the potential for trophic transfer fish and larger vertebrates including humans. The assessment of macro litter and microplastics highlighted major concerns regarding implications on both ecosystem and human health.

In terms of the Ave estuary region, there are many activities that can be impacted by the presence of ML.

Impact on fisheries

Fishing is one of the major economic activities in Portugal. In fact, Portugal is ranked fifth among countries in the European Union (EU-27) in terms of people employed in the fisheries industry. The importance of the fishery in Portugal is also reflected in the existing support to the fisheries sectors from the national, regional and local governments through a wide range of policies. The objectives of those policies are centred on goals such as maintaining employment, improving fishers' welfare, or ensuring the sustainability of the sector and the resources it relies on (OECD, 2021).

The country has a long tradition in the sector, and is the largest consumer of seafood in Europe and one of the four countries in the world with a seafood-based diet, being among the countries in the world with the highest fish consumption per capita (Pessoa et al., 2006). The Portuguese fishing sector is divided between industrial fishing and artisanal fishing, and the fishing vessels can be classified according to the area in which they operate: local fishing vessels, coastal fishing vessels and long-distance fishing vessels. In 2021, small vessels, with a gross tonnage of less than 5 GT, accounted for 83.8 % of the total number of fishing vessels and large vessels (more than 100 GT) contributed 2.2 % (INE, 2023). Small-scale fisheries in Portugal have a high social, economic and cultural importance; with Portuguese culture and traditions deeply rooted in fishing and with fishing being the economic basis of many communities characterised by low economic diversification (Pita and Gaspar, 2020). So the majority of the fishing activities in Portugal are located at local or coastal fishing regions, which are more prone to the impact of ML generated from terrestrial sources and transported to the sea. In fact, the Portuguese fishing industry has to absorb the annual costs resulting from damage to vessels caused by floating and abandoned debris and losses of fishing gear (APA, 2023⁹), with strong impacts on this economic activity. This is why many activities and research projects have been addressed to improve waste management on board fishing vessels, sensitise and support fishermen in adopting good environmental practices and improve the environmental conditions of the coastal zone and preserve marine ecosystems (DocaPesca, 2023¹⁰).

⁹ <https://apambiente.pt/residuos/lixo-marinho>

¹⁰ <http://www.marsemlixo.com/>

The area around the MAELSTROM Portuguese demo site presents several fishing marinas. In the closest region, two of them can be found, the smallest one located inside the Ave River estuary and the largest one close to the mouth of the estuary in the northern municipality of Póvoa de Varzim. To the south, inside the Leixões Port, in Matosinhos municipality, there is another fishing marina, as well as inside the Douro River estuary. This northern region of Portugal, where the Ave River estuary is located, presents a strong tradition of artisanal fishing, and historically, the fishery was one of the main economic activities.

In addition to the fishing activities, Portugal also presents many canned fish processing plants. The mainland's principal ports specialised in canning small pelagic fish are Peniche, Olhão and the Matosinhos-Póvoa de Varzim area where the Ave River Estuary is located.

Impact on coastal tourism and recreational activities

As a country located in the southern region of Europe, the climatological conditions of Portugal makes it an attractive region for different touristic activities. In 2017, the country was voted "Best Destination in the World " at the World Travel Awards, and regained the title in 2018 and 2019. In 2022, overnight stays totalled 69.7 million, considering Portuguese residents but also non-residents. For the same year, it was estimated that Portugal would have received 22.3 million non-resident tourists (Turismo de Portugal, 2023). This economic activity, which brings an important amount of receipts for the Portuguese economy (€21.1 billion in 2022), has been increasing over the years, with a number of overnight stays per 100 inhabitants for the entire Portugal that increases from 328,4 in 2000 to 667,3 in 2022 (Pordata, 2023¹¹). Exceptions to this trend are the years 2020 and 2021 due to COVID pandemic. Similar trends are observed for the northern coast of Portugal, with the larger increase observed in the Porto city region, with a number of overnight stays per 100 inhabitants that increases from 365,9 in 2001 to 2.022,3 in 2022 (Pordata, 2023).

The main tourism segments that can be found in Portugal are sun and sea tourism, residential tourism, sports tourism (including water and underwater sports, and fishing), business tourism, urban tourism, cultural tourism, rural tourism, ecotourism and nature, adventure tourism, health tourism, religious tourism and cruise ships. Among being an increased source of ML by themselves, these sectors can also be

¹¹ <http://www.marsemlixo.com/>

affected by the presence of ML, not only by their aesthetical aspect, but also by the effects on the activities, particularly on the sun and beach, sports, ecotourism and nature and cruise ships tourism.

Impact on protected natural areas and valuable ecosystem

Considering Portugal peninsular mainland and the Atlantic archipelagos of Madeira and the Azores, the protected areas cover a total of 76,975 km² at sea, and represents the third largest marine protected areas network in the EU. Portugal has a total of 414 protected areas, comprising 247 sites designated under national laws (National Network of Protected Areas - RNAP) and 167 recognized as Natura 2000 sites (Special Areas of Conservation - ZEC). These Natura 2000 sites are designated under the Birds Directive, encompassing 62 Special Protection Areas, and the Habitats Directive, encompassing 108 Sites of Community Importance. Many sites are designated under both Directives (Biodiversity Europe, 2023¹²). The main protected areas of northern Portugal that can be affected by the ML generated in the Ave River estuary are represented in Figure 7. It includes two RNAP (Parque Natural do Litoral Norte and Paisagem Protegida Regional do Litoral de Vila do Conde e Reserva Ornitológica de Mindelo) and two ZEC (Litoral Norte and Maceda/Praia da Vieira).

¹² <https://biodiversity.europa.eu/>

Figure 7. Spatial distribution of protected areas network of northern Portugal. The red dot represents the location of the MAELSTROM Portuguese demo site (Ave River estuary). Source Biodiversity Europe, 2023

The southern coastline of the Vila do Conde municipality has the Vila do Conde Coastal Regional Protected Landscape and Mindelo Ornithological Reserve (Paisagem Protegida Regional do Litoral de Vila do Conde e Reserva Ornitológica de Mindelo). In this 8.5-kilometre-long coastline with a total area of 380 ha, a wide range of biological and landscape values are present. The habitat mosaic includes coastal sand dunes, rocks, wetlands, bushlands and crop fields. Flora includes several Portuguese endemic species, with highlight *Coincya johnstonii* and *Jasione maritima* var. *sabularia* in coastal sand dunes. The occurrence of 81 species was confirmed, with more than half (54 %) of the species observed after 1990 being resident, but migratory species accounting for 28 % of the total. Of the 81 species, 57 have a conservation status in accordance with one or more of the main Community Directives or International Conventions, with a high number of species covered by the Bern Convention on the protection of migratory species (33 species). From an ornithological point of view, the most important areas for birdlife are the Ave River estuary, the adjacent beach and marsh area, and the original area of the Mindelo Ornithological Reserve. Other animals can be found here such as amphibians and reptiles, for example *Anguis fragilis* or the Iberian endemic *Lacerta schreiberi*. There

are also mammals, such as the weasel *Mustela nivalis*, the hedgehog *Erinaceus europaeus* and the squirrel *Sciurus vulgaris*, as well as a notable presence of invertebrate species and fish, the latter of which are still little studied (ICNF, 2023¹³).

This region is an area of great historical and symbolic value for its pioneering role in nature conservation. The Mindelo Ornithological Reserve was the first protected area created in Portugal. In pursuit of its sustainable development strategy, the Vila do Conde city council, together with the Porto Metropolitan Council, took all the necessary steps to have the south coast of Vila do Conde classified as a regional protected area. This classification, made official by a decision of the Porto Metropolitan Assembly - Notice no. 17821/2009, of 12 October, DR 2nd series, has the effect of enabling the adoption of effective measures to maintain and enhance biological diversity and the character of the landscape and to mitigate certain environmental and aesthetic dissonances (CMVC, 2023¹⁴).

To the north of the Ave estuary mouth, the Litoral Norte Nature Park (Parque Natural do Litoral Norte) can also be found. This Protected Area was created with the aim of conserving its natural, physical, aesthetic, landscape and cultural values. The area of this Natural Park is 8,761.81 ha, of which 7,703 ha is marine and the remaining 1,072 ha island, and it sprawls through 16 km of the coast from Neiva Estuary to Apúlia area where the windmills are an evident visual reference. This park contains sea and river beaches, primary and secondary dunes, reefs, the headland of the Cávado river, coastal lagoons, and marine habitats. The estuaries of Cávado and Neiva rivers, spots of pine woods, oak woodland, crop fields, some small leafy woods and reed beds contribute to the plant diversity with around 240 species. This is also an area with intense agricultural activity. This coast was used to catch seaweeds for land fertilisation. The marine area is characterised by numerous shallows and in the area covered by the Park the depths do not exceed 50 metres. (Natural, 2023¹⁵; ICNF, 2023).

Paying attention to the Nature 2000 network, there are several regions that can also be impacted by the ML of the Ave River estuary due to the dynamic conditions of the Portuguese coastline. River plumes are a common feature. Freshwater discharges from rivers into the coastal ocean may cause a front with the more saline waters, inhibiting the mixing, and a northward coastal countercurrent, transporting materials

¹³ www.icnf.pt

¹⁴ www.cm-viladoconde.pt

¹⁵ natural.pt

along the coast. In addition to this process, the more frequent wave direction (NW) produces a southward drift current that can also transport terrestrial materials, and so ML to other locations (Viitak et al., 2021; Bastos et al., 2016). The two regions closer to the Ave River estuary that can be affected by the ML transported by the river plumes generated current or by the drift current are the Parque natural do Litoral Norte (to the north of the Ave region) and the Maceda/Praia da Vieira (to the south of the Ave region).

The Litoral Norte (PTCON0017), protected under the Habitats Directive and established in 1998, has an area of 2798,03 ha that not only encompasses marine but also terrestrial areas. It presents 14 habitats to be preserved, including marine habitats such as Atlantic salt meadows, reefs, and sandbanks which are slightly covered by sea water all the time, and 5 species, including mayfish (*Alosa alosa*), salmon (*Salmo salar*) and twaite shad (*Alosa fallax*). The region Maceda/Praia da Vieira (PTCON0063), also protected under the Habitats Directive, was established in 2001 and presents an area of 502637 ha. It is a marine protected area with 2 habitats, including reefs and sandbanks which are slightly covered by sea water all the time, and 6 species, including bottle-nosed dolphin (*Tursiops truncatus*), harbour porpoise (*Phocoena phocoena*), loggerhead turtle (*Caretta caretta*), mayfish (*Alosa alosa*), sea lamprey (*Petromyzon marinus*), and twaite shad (*Alosa fallax*) (Natura 2000¹⁶).

¹⁶ <https://natura2000.eea.europa.eu/>

6 The role of marine planning in marine litter management

The degree of consideration of ML pollution issues in MSP plans differs across the EU countries, in relation with the different approaches to planning and the different mandates given to MSP at national level. Pollution prevention (and remediation) generally does not fall under the principal scope of MSP that targets mainly the resolution of sea use conflicts. ML pollution prevention is considered to a larger degree in the scope of the Programmes of Measures (PoM), developed under the provisions of the MSFD where ML is targeted under Descriptor 10. Notwithstanding this, several MSP plans, among those analysed for this study, recognize the relevance of the issue by including at least some reference to the topic.

MSP plans, even if they do not address ML directly, recognize it as a critical anthropogenic pressure and maritime activities (fisheries, shipping, etc) as important sources of ML too. Some MSP plans address specifically the need to contribute to ML pollution prevention by including objectives and measures targeting maritime sectors and activities. This implies acknowledging the co-responsibility of sectors and the need for concerted action across the full life-cycle of (plastic) waste, recognizing also that the critical component of the management and prevention of ML is beyond the maritime domain and needs to be managed across the land-sea interface. Particularly interesting are those plans that also account for a terrestrial coastal strip, since coastal tourism and recreation on the coast are one of the most important sources of ML and also one of the highest impacted sectors, with coastal municipalities and/or beach managers spending significant budgets to clean up their beaches.

Generally, a growing need for integration between MSFD and MSPD is being recognized¹⁷. This link should definitely be reinforced under different aspects: the improved coherence of data and tools to assess the state of the sea is an important aspect to be targeted; data from MSFD should be more and more available and used for MSP plans. Monitoring efforts under the MSFD have generated a good knowledge of the scale and characteristics of the ML pollution problem which now can feed into (and even has helped design) other EU policies, including MSP. Stronger linkage in the objectives between MSP and MSFD should also be pursued, being the GES of marine

¹⁷ European Commission - DG Environment. Informal meeting of EU water directors and EU marine directors, Constanța, România, 13 June 2019

waters the common overarching goal, with MSFD provisions defining what GES is meant and MSP plans organising sea uses and activity, in a way to guarantee the achievement and maintenance of GES. Ultimately, enhanced synergies and complementarities between the PoMs and MSP plan provisions should be achieved.

In addition to that, it is crucial to consider the need for a stronger linkage between WFD and MSFD too, with particular regard to the topic of ML pollution. MSFD addresses ML in terms of Beach Litter, Floating Litter, Litter in Biota and Microlitter in the assessment of GES for EU marine waters. On the other hand, the Environmental Quality Standards of the WFD do not include plastic litter as a pollutant but only suspended micro and nanoplastics. Plastic litter is also not being considered to be included in the upcoming Directive's "Watch List" since it's absent from the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (*JRC*) report (Cortes et al., 2022).

MSP is a tool to help integrating activities undertaken at sea under different policies, and the overarching objective of ecosystem approach and sustainable use of resources, MSP is called to be able to integrate more and more environmental sustainability issues.

Particularly in the case of ML, it is important for marine planners to consider that the maritime and coastal economic sectors and the sea-use in general, which the MSP aims to develop and coordinate, are both negatively impacted by ML pollution and, at the same time, they also act as a source for this type of pollution. It is therefore important that MSP plans consider ML pollution as one important informative layer to develop spatial scenarios for uses, taking into consideration the impact that this type of pollution causes on the full spectrum of economic sectors. At the same time, MSP plans should include provisions in order to coordinate with and reinforce provisions from other maritime and non-maritime policies, including sectorial ones, in the direction of pollution prevention (which usually starts mostly on land). ML pollution remediation (clean-ups of beaches, sea bottom, canals, etc.) should be also taken into consideration, depending on the nature and state of pollution in the geographic scope of the plan. Such remediation actions can also generate important data to characterise ML pollution and even monitor the impact of prevention measures (developed under MSFD, Zero Pollution Action Plan, Single-Use Plastics Directive, etc).

A number of policies are available at international and European level to help maritime sectors and planners addressing ML related issues. An increasing number

of valuable practices is also becoming available at EU and regional sea level, thanks to the efforts of science, the sectors and the civil society.

It is important that marine planners, and the general public, are aware of the portfolio of solutions to prevent, understand and manage ML pollution including its remediation. To this regard, the project MAELSTROM offers numerical models to predict the transport of ML in the environment that can support the identification of ML hotspots. The project also offers two innovative technologies for ML remediation. The first one is a robotic seabed cleaning platform developed by TECNALIA, CNRS-LIRMM and Servizi Tecnici, which allows to reach the seabed of lagoons, rivers, estuaries, ports and coastal areas to remove ML including macro plastics. This technology also identifies ML and picks each item selectively to minimise the impact on ecosystems. The second technology is a bubble barrier, developed by The Great Bubble Barrier, an innovative and sustainable technology that catches plastic pollution in rivers, estuaries and channels before it reaches the ocean, using a bubble curtain fed by a compressor that, jointly with the strength of the currents, conducts the litter to a catchment system located in one of the margins. Within the MAELSTROM project, the bubble barrier will be co-powered through solar panels developed by the University of Malta.

The following table provides an overview of some main ML sources, impacts, EU policies and other initiatives relevant to maritime sectors. This table is aimed at providing a snapshot on the topic for planners, decision-makers and practitioners.

Table 4. Percentage Main ML sources, impacts, EU policies and other initiatives relevant for maritime sectors.

Economic sector/uses of the sea		As Source of ML	Impacted by ML	Policies	Other solutions accessible to planners
		Is it a source of litter? Which types?	What sort of ML impacts this sector is subject to? By which type of ML?	Which specific EU policies target ML from this sector?	Which actions can help prevent/remediate ML from this sector?
Maritime	Nature protection (MPAs, N2K, other protected areas)	No	Ghost fishing and entanglement by Abandoned, lost or otherwise discarded fishing gear (ALDFG); Invasive species by plastic litter (diffuse, transboundary sources); Ingestion of plastic (e.g. bags, consumer plastics) by protected species (e.g. cetaceans);	N.A.	Underwater clean-up by volunteering recreational divers (e.g. "Project Aware", "Healthy Seas") Sea-floor clean-up - MAELSTROM pilot; Riverine litter removal - MAELSTROM pilot;

Economic sector/uses of the sea		As Source of ML	Impacted by ML	Policies	Other solutions accessible to planners
		Is it a source of litter? Which types?	What sort of ML impacts this sector is subject to? By which type of ML?	Which specific EU policies target ML from this sector?	Which actions can help prevent/remediate ML from this sector?
	Fisheries	ALDFG, ropes and cords, fish boxes, rubber gloves, floats/buoys, other plastic litter	Reduced catches Reduced quality of catch due to litter ingestion; Time/effort lost in removing litter from fishing gear Damages to gears and propellers Accidents at sea, e.g. propeller entanglement by ropes/nets	Single-Use Plastics (SUP) Directive (Directive (EU) 2019/904) MSFD (Directive 2008/56/EC) Port Reception Facilities Directive (Directive EU 2019/883) Regulation (EC) 1224/2009 for a Community control system and its Commission Implementing Regulation (EC) 404/2011 Decision (EU) 2021/958 on data and information on fishing gear placed on the market and waste fishing gear collected	Circular design of fishing gears (EC, 2020) "Fishing for Litter" initiatives. Extended Producers Responsibility (EPR) schemes for Fishing gears Source-based solutions found with local stakeholders: adequate deck cleaning operations + containers Waste reception facilities, including for fishing gear, at fishing harbours.

Economic sector/uses of the sea		As Source of ML	Impacted by ML	Policies	Other solutions accessible to planners
		Is it a source of litter? Which types?	What sort of ML impacts this sector is subject to? By which type of ML?	Which specific EU policies target ML from this sector?	Which actions can help prevent/remediate ML from this sector?
	Aquaculture	Nets, plastic sheeting from mussel culture, floats/buoys, etc	Clean-up costs by all sorts of ML; Lower quality of products and risk to human health (i.e. microplastics ingestion).	MSFD (Directive 2008/56/EC) Strategic guidelines for a more sustainable and competitive EU aquaculture for the period 2021 to 2030	Circular design of fishing gears (EC, 2020) "Fishing for Litter" initiatives. Extended Producers Responsibility (EPR) schemes for Fishing gears Sea-floor clean-up within aquaculture site - MAELSTROM pilot;
	Shipping	Ropes and cords, containers, tetra packs and other (illegally dumped) galley waste, lubricants and other maintenance containers, etc. Container ship accidents	Accidents at sea, e.g. propeller entanglement by ropes/nets (e.g. Fisheries, Shipping, Harbours, etc), clogging of pumps (ML from diffuse sources);	MARPOL 73/78 (Annex V, plastic and garbage disposal) Port Reception Facilities Directive (EU) 2019/883 MSFD (Directive 2008/56/EC)	Port reception facilities and "no special fee"
	Recreational vessels	(Illegally dumped) galley waste End-of-life boats illegally abandoned	Accidents at sea, e.g. propeller entanglement by ropes/nets (e.g. Fisheries, Shipping, Harbours, etc);	MSFD (Directive 2008/56/EC)	Circular design of recreational boats Extended Producers Responsibility (EPR) Blue Flag initiative (for marinas)

Economic sector/uses of the sea		As Source of ML	Impacted by ML	Policies	Other solutions accessible to planners
		Is it a source of litter? Which types?	What sort of ML impacts this sector is subject to? By which type of ML?	Which specific EU policies target ML from this sector?	Which actions can help prevent/remediate ML from this sector?
	Cruise ships	(Illegally released) consumer waste	Accidents at sea, e.g. propeller entanglement by ropes/nets (e.g. from Fisheries, Shipping, Harbours, etc); clogging of pumps (ML from diffuse sources);	MARPOL 73/78 (Annex V, plastic and garbage disposal) MSFD (Directive 2008/56/EC)	Good practices e.g. green purchasing and agreement, increasing public awareness, staff training, consumption reduction, etc (ref. Beyond Plastic Med Good Practice Guide)
Coastal	Beach tourism	Consumer plastic waste, such as drink bottles, plastic bags, food wrappers, crisp/sweets packets, cigarette butts, etc (littered, wind-blown)	Loss of aesthetic value by all sorts of ML (land and sea-based sources); Clean-up costs during bathing season.	SUP Directive (Directive (EU) 2019/904); MSFD (Directive 2008/56/EC); Bathing Water Quality Directive	Beach clean-up volunteering initiatives (e.g. Let's Clean up Europe, Marine Litter Watch, World Clean-up Day, etc); EPR schemes (e.g. clean-up costs); Blue Flag initiative; Riverine litter removal - MAELSTROM pilot;
	Coastal recreational events	Consumer plastic waste, mainly drink and food packaging, cigarette butts, etc.	Clean-up costs of area of the event	SUP Directive (Directive (EU) 2019/904); MSFD (Directive 2008/56/EC)	Best practices for (plastic) waste prevention (e.g. drinks cups that are reusable/deposit-refund)

Economic sector/uses of the sea		As Source of ML	Impacted by ML	Policies	Other solutions accessible to planners
		Is it a source of litter? Which types?	What sort of ML impacts this sector is subject to? By which type of ML?	Which specific EU policies target ML from this sector?	Which actions can help prevent/remediate ML from this sector?
	Ports and Harbours	Containers, ALDFG, ropes and cords, fish boxes, etc	Accumulation of litter in port areas	Port Reception Facilities Directive; MSFD	ALDFG collection and recycling (e.g. "HealthySeas") EPR schemes (e.g. collection of fishing gear at end-of-life). Sea-floor clean-up within port area (MAELSTROM pilot)

7 Suggestions to planners on how to consider ML pollution in marine plans

Based on the elements illustrated in the present deliverable, the following suggestions are addressed to planners, MSP authorities and practitioners for a better consideration of ML pollution issue in marine plans:

Analysing existing conditions

1. Consider ML data from MSFD monitoring and other reliable data sources. to take into consideration ML distribution in stocktaking.
2. Consider the application of numerical models (including those developed in the MAELSTROM project) to simulate distribution and hot-spots of accumulation of ML
3. Engage in dialogue with institutions responsible for MSFD monitoring and with other actors active in ML monitoring (NGOs, citizen science projects).
4. Consider and capitalise on studies addressing analysis of ML spatial distribution in the environment and spatial distribution of the maritime and coastal activities in the area, to understand possible sources-pathways/transport-accumulation. This is particularly relevant to assess how maritime and coastal activities are generating ML what can be their role in preventing/managing it, as well as identify marine areas that may be more highly impacted by ML (e.g. Marine Protected Areas and areas of high recreational value).
5. Understand the role of land-based and sea-based sources on ML pollution in the area.
6. Include ML pollution in the topics considered by land-sea-interaction analysis, undertaken under MSP.

Developing the plan (including identification of objectives and spatial + non-spatial measures)

1. Include objectives related with ML pollution prevention from maritime sectors.

2. Include non-spatial measures related with ML pollution prevention from maritime sectors, particularly those that can be articulated/aligned with the PoMs.
3. Consider including ML remediation measures focusing on pollution hotspots which are particularly impacting maritime uses (including marine protection) and economic activities (e.g. fishing, beach tourism). Furthermore, these remediation measures can generate important data on litter quantities and amounts, which can, in turn, help inform other policies, including those targeting production, consumption and waste management.
4. Enhance synergies with ML pollution measures eventually included in the PoM under MSFD, or complement them.
5. Enhance synergies with ML pollution measures eventually included in coastal plans or River Basin Management Plans (WFD).
6. If knowledge gaps are present, foresee monitoring and studies addressing ML pollution sources and impacts related with maritime activities.

Stakeholder engagement (supporting all MSP stages)

1. Engage in dialogue with maritime sectors to understand the economic impact of ML pollution on their activities.
2. Engage in dialogue with actors responsible for key activities on the mainland, recognized as (most probable) sources of ML to identify possible coordinated measures.
3. Encourage maritime sectors to engage in and support citizen science and community monitoring and cleanup initiatives. Encourage maritime sectors to develop educational and outreach activities for ocean literacy and active participation in responsible citizenship.
4. Engage in dialogue with institutions responsible for the quality of marine waters and sediments (at the national, regional or local level, depending on the scale of the plan) to discuss possible options for ML pollution prevention.

5. Engage with institutions responsible for the quality of marine waters and sediments to discuss possible remediation activities in specific hotspots, prioritising those areas most impacting the activities of maritime sectors.

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Annex 1 - Questionnaire on the consideration of Marine Litter issues and management in Maritime Spatial Planning and Coastal Zone management

Country	
Type of plan (MSP, ICM)	
Governance level of the plan	<input type="checkbox"/> National <input type="checkbox"/> Sub-national (regional) <input type="checkbox"/> Local (municipality, county)
Geographic scope of the plan	<input type="checkbox"/> Only terrestrial <input type="checkbox"/> Terrestrial with a coastal marine strip <input type="checkbox"/> Terrestrial and marine <input type="checkbox"/> Marine with a coastal terrestrial strip <input type="checkbox"/> Only marine
Does the plan consider ML related issues?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, in stocktaking Please explain <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, within the main MSP issues Please explain <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, in the vision Please explain <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, in the objectives Please explain <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, in the measures Please explain <input type="checkbox"/> No, not at all
(if yes) Does the plan target land-based or sea-based ML pollution?	<input type="checkbox"/> Only land-based <input type="checkbox"/> Only sea-based <input type="checkbox"/> Both
(if yes) Does the plan target ML pollution prevention or remediation?	<input type="checkbox"/> Only prevention <input type="checkbox"/> Only remediation <input type="checkbox"/> Both

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<p>(if yes)</p> <p>In relation to ML pollution prevention, what sectors are targeted by the plan?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Tourism: bathing <input type="checkbox"/> Tourism: nautical <input type="checkbox"/> Tourism: cruise <input type="checkbox"/> Tourism: coastal <input type="checkbox"/> Fishing: professional <input type="checkbox"/> Fishing: recreational <input type="checkbox"/> Aquaculture <input type="checkbox"/> Shipping <input type="checkbox"/> Ports <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture <input type="checkbox"/> Industry (specify typology, are they offshore, coastal or inland?) <input type="checkbox"/> Urban sources
<p>(if yes)</p> <p>In relation to ML pollution prevention, what kind of other actions (not related to economic sectors) are foreseen by the plan?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Improvements in waste management (general) <input type="checkbox"/> encourage collection of waste from fishing activities (e.g. facilities in harbours to deliver old fishing nets) <input type="checkbox"/> encourage collection of waste from shipping (e.g. port reception facilities) <input type="checkbox"/> awareness raising among professionals to prevent litter pollution (e.g. fishermen) <input type="checkbox"/> restriction/reduction of certain activities/materials/products (e.g. types/materials of fishing gear, boxes) <input type="checkbox"/> other actions to improve waste management (please specify) <p>Please explain</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Infrastructures for ML pollution prevention (e.g. barriers) <p>Please explain</p>
<p>(if yes)</p> <p>What kind of remediation actions are foreseen by the plan?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Fishing for litter <input type="checkbox"/> Beach cleaning <input type="checkbox"/> Bank cleaning <input type="checkbox"/> Floating litter removal <input type="checkbox"/> Sea-bed litter removal <input type="checkbox"/> Other <p>Please specify</p>

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<p>(if yes)</p> <p>Does the plan foresee actions from a circular economy perspective?</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, reuse/recycling of ML collected from the sea (including beach litter)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes, reuse/recycling of waste generated by maritime sectors (e.g. end-of-life fishing and aquaculture gears).</p>
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